

Assessing the Impact of Online Civic Education Platforms on Educator Competency and Student Outcomes: A Case of Selected Higher Learning Institutions in Zambia

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Abstract:

Overview: The integration of online Civic Education platforms in the educational landscape has emerged as a pivotal strategy in enhancing both educator competency and student outcomes. This study aimed to assess the multifaceted impact of these digital tools on the teaching and learning process within civic education in Zambian higher learning institutions.

Body of Knowledge: The study investigated the correlation between the use of online civic education platforms and student performance. It examined the extent to which these digital resources enhance students' civic knowledge, critical thinking skills, and participation in civic activities. The interactive features of online platforms, such as discussion forums, quizzes, and multimedia content, are analyzed to understand their role in creating an engaging learning environment that supports diverse learning styles.

Methods: A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative data from surveys and academic performance records with qualitative insights from interviews and focus groups. This comprehensive methodology allowed for a nuanced understanding of the impact of online civic education platforms. The population sampled 200 respondents, consisting of university lecturers and students from 5 selected higher learning institutions in Lusaka district of Zambia that have implemented online civic education platforms. Questionnaires and surveys were used to collect quantitative data while interviews and focus groups were used to collect qualitative data from the participants. The study used appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS and Microsoft Excel as well as research themes to analyze data.

Results: *The findings noted that online civic education platforms significantly enhance educator competency by providing access to up-to-date resources, training, and pedagogical tools that improve teaching strategies and engagement with students. The platforms facilitate personalized learning, allowing students to explore topics at their own pace and apply knowledge in real-world contexts. However, the study also identified challenges, such as varying levels of digital literacy among educators and students, and the need for continuous support and training to maximize the benefits of these platforms.*

Recommendation: *The study recommended for educators to focus on evaluating enhancements in teaching practices, engagement strategies, and overall competency in delivering civic education content. For students, the assessment should measure improvements in civic knowledge, critical thinking skills, and participatory behaviors.*

Keywords: *Civic Education, Competency, Online Platforms, Student Outcomes, and Technology.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Civic education is a critical component of a well-rounded education system, aimed at equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to participate effectively in democratic processes and society (Chanda et al, 2024). This educational field focuses on teaching students about their rights and responsibilities as citizens, the structure and functioning of government institutions, and the principles of democracy. Effective civic education programs encourage active participation, critical thinking, and an understanding of civic duties, thereby fostering a sense of belonging and engagement in the community. Muleya (2019) says that civic education as a subject taught in schools equips learners with the knowledge and skills for them to understand their rights and duties, critically engage with public affairs, and contribute to a just and sustainable society. By integrating discussions on governance, civil rights, and social issues, and civic education helps students become informed, responsible, and active members of society. In contemporary contexts, civic education also encompasses the use of digital platforms and online resources, which can enhance accessibility and engagement but also present challenges in ensuring the accuracy and reliability of information. Overall, robust civic education plays a crucial role in preparing individuals to contribute to and shape democratic societies, making it a fundamental element of educational curricula (Mtonga & Magasu, 2024).

Competency refers to the combination of knowledge, skills, abilities, and behaviors that an individual needs to effectively perform a specific role or task (Winthrop, 2020). It encompasses both the theoretical understanding and practical application required to achieve desired outcomes. Competency is not merely about possessing knowledge but involves the capability to apply that knowledge in real-world situations, adapt to varying contexts, and solve problems efficiently. It integrates cognitive abilities, technical skills, and interpersonal qualities, allowing individuals to

meet the demands of their roles and contribute meaningfully to their organizations or fields of study. Competency is crucial for professional and personal development as it ensures that individuals are not only proficient in their tasks but also capable of continuous improvement and adaptation in a dynamic environment (Mpolomoka et al, 2023). Competency in civic education encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for individuals to effectively engage in democratic processes and contribute to their communities. It involves a deep understanding of democratic principles, governmental structures, and the rights and responsibilities of citizens. Mulemwa & Chanda (2023) alluded that competency in civic education is not limited to theoretical knowledge; it also includes practical skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and active participation in civic activities. This competence is cultivated through a well-designed curriculum that integrates civic learning with real-world applications, encourages reflective practices, and fosters a sense of agency among learners. By developing these competencies, individuals are better equipped to make informed decisions, advocate for social justice, and engage in constructive dialogues, thereby enhancing the overall health and effectiveness of democratic systems.

Technology has revolutionized online platforms, transforming the way we interact, learn, and conduct business. Zohaib et al (2024)' study noted that online platforms leverage advancements in digital technology to provide a variety of services and functions, from social networking to e-commerce and education. They facilitate instant communication and access to information, breaking down geographical barriers and enabling global connectivity. For instance, in education, technology-enabled online platforms offer e-learning environments where students can access resources, participate in virtual classrooms, and engage in collaborative projects. These platforms support diverse learning styles and needs, providing interactive and multimedia content that can enhance understanding and retention. Furthermore, technology integrates advanced tools like artificial intelligence and data analytics to personalize learning experiences and track progress (Schmid et al, 2020). As technology continues to evolve, online platforms are likely to become even more integral to daily life, offering innovative solutions and expanding opportunities across various domains.

Online platforms refer to digital environments or systems that facilitate various types of interactions, transactions, or services over the internet (Chanda et al, 2024). They can encompass a wide range of applications, from social media networks and e-commerce sites to educational tools and collaborative workspaces. These platforms leverage technology to connect users, provide resources, and enable communication or commerce. In the context of education, online platforms often serve as virtual classrooms, providing access to learning materials, enabling real-time interaction between students and educators, and supporting a range of educational activities. They can enhance learning experiences by offering flexible access to resources, promoting collaboration, and accommodating diverse learning styles (Alma et al, 2024). Online platforms in

civic education have revolutionized the way civic knowledge and engagement are fostered among students and educators. These platforms provide a dynamic and interactive learning environment where users can access a wide range of resources, including multimedia content, discussion forums, and real-time feedback mechanisms. By utilizing digital tools, online platforms offer flexibility and accessibility, allowing learners to engage with civic education materials at their own pace and from various locations. This approach not only enhances the reach of civic education but also supports diverse learning styles and needs (M’cormack, 2011). Furthermore, online platforms often incorporate gamification and simulation exercises, which can make learning about democratic processes and civic responsibilities more engaging and practical. The integration of these platforms into the curriculum can lead to increased educator competency as teachers become adept at using digital tools and methods, ultimately improving student outcomes by providing more relevant and contemporary educational experiences.

Student outcomes refer to the measurable achievements or results that indicate the extent to which students have acquired knowledge, skills, and attitudes as a result of their educational experiences (Chanda, 2024). These outcomes can encompass a range of academic and non-academic achievements, including improved academic performance, enhanced critical thinking abilities, and increased engagement in civic activities. Effective educational programs aim to achieve positive student outcomes by implementing well-designed curricula, employing effective teaching strategies, and providing supportive learning environments (Mainde et al, 2022). Assessing student outcomes involves evaluating various metrics such as test scores, graduation rates, and student feedback to gauge the success of educational interventions and to inform future instructional practices. Monitoring and improving student outcomes is crucial for ensuring that educational institutions fulfill their mission of preparing students for future success and active participation in society.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The problem addressed in this study is the growing need to evaluate the effectiveness of online civic education platforms in enhancing both educator competency and student outcomes within Zambian higher learning institutions. Chanda & Zohaib (2024) says that with the increasing adoption of digital tools in education, there is a significant shift towards online platforms for delivering civic education. However, the impact of these platforms on the quality of instruction and student learning outcomes remains underexplored. In Zambian higher learning institutions, where traditional teaching methods have long been the norm, the transition to online civic education poses challenges in terms of both educator preparedness and student engagement (Mainde et al, 2021). This study sought to assess how well these online platforms contribute to improving educators' ability to deliver civic education effectively and enhance students' understanding of civic responsibilities and democratic values. The findings aimed to provide insights into the potential benefits and limitations of online civic education platforms, guiding

future strategies for integrating digital tools into civic education programs and ensuring they meet educational objectives and standards.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of online civic education platforms in enhancing both educator competency and student outcomes within selected higher learning institutions in Zambia.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- To evaluate the effectiveness of online civic education platforms in enhancing educator competency within selected higher learning institutions in Lusaka Zambia.
- To assess the impact of online civic education platforms on student learning outcomes within selected higher learning institutions in Lusaka Zambia.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Social Learning Theory. The theory was proposed by Albert Bandura which emphasized the role of observational learning, imitation, and modeling in the acquisition of new behaviors and skills. In the context of online civic education platforms, this theory can provide valuable insights into how educators and students interact with and benefit from these digital tools. According to the theory, educators can enhance their competency by observing and adapting successful teaching practices modeled by their peers on these platforms. Similarly, students may learn civic knowledge and skills more effectively by engaging with interactive content, observing peer behaviors, and participating in discussions (Chanda, 2024). Assessing the impact of these online platforms involves examining how well educators can implement best practices learned through observation and how students' competencies in civic education improve through these digital interactions. This approach helps in understanding whether online civic education platforms effectively contribute to both educator development and student learning outcomes by leveraging the principles of social learning.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its potential to provide valuable insights into how online civic education platforms influence both educator competency and student outcomes within the context of Zambian higher learning institutions. By evaluating the effectiveness of these digital tools, the study aimed to determine how they can enhance educators' ability to teach civic education and improve students' understanding and engagement with civic issues. This study was particularly pertinent given the increasing reliance on digital technologies in education and the growing need for effective civic education to foster informed and active citizenship. The findings may inform policy makers, educational leaders, and curriculum developers about the benefits and challenges of incorporating online platforms into civic education, ultimately contributing to more effective teaching strategies and improved educational outcomes in Zambian higher education.

2. METHODOLOGY

A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative data from surveys and questionnaires with qualitative insights from interviews and focus groups. This comprehensive methodology allowed for a nuanced understanding of the impact of online civic education

platforms. The study also considered various contextual factors, such as socioeconomic status and access to technology, which may influence both educator and student experiences with these platforms. The target population was 2000 and sampled 200 respondents which was 10% of the targeted number. The sample consisted 20 university lecturers, 4 representing each selected institution, and 180 students, 36 representing each selected institution from the 5 selected higher learning institutions in Lusaka district of Zambia that have implemented online civic education platforms. The study made use of the questionnaires, and surveys to collect quantitative data while interviews and focus groups were used to collect qualitative data from the participants. The quantitative data collected were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) and Microsoft Excel whereas the qualitative data were analyzed thematically. The study upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Effectiveness of Online Civic Education Platforms in Enhancing Educator Competency within Selected Higher Learning Institutions

According to research findings, the rise of online civic education platforms has significantly impacted various aspects of the educational landscape, particularly in enhancing educator competency.

3.1.1 Benefits of Online Civic Education Platforms

The study results noted that online civic education platforms offer the significant benefit of providing updated content, ensuring that both educators and students have access to the most current information and resources. Unlike traditional textbooks, which can quickly become outdated, online platforms can be easily and frequently updated to reflect the latest developments in civic issues, policies, and events (Rui, 2022). This timeliness is crucial in civic education, where understanding current affairs, emerging social movements, and evolving legal frameworks are essential for fostering informed and engaged citizens. Moreover, online platforms can integrate diverse perspectives and multimedia resources, such as videos, interactive simulations, and real-time data, which enrich the learning experience and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter (Zohaib et al, 2024). This dynamic content delivery helps educators stay relevant and supports students in developing critical thinking skills and a deeper awareness of their civic environment.

Additionally, collaborative learning is a significant benefit of online civic education platforms, fostering an interactive and engaging environment where students can actively participate and learn from each other. These platforms enable learners from diverse backgrounds to come together in virtual spaces, promoting the exchange of ideas, perspectives, and experiences related to civic issues (Chanda, 2023). Through discussion forums, group projects, and peer reviews, students can

collaboratively analyze social, political, and economic topics, enhancing their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The collaborative nature of these platforms also encourages students to develop communication and teamwork skills, as they must articulate their ideas clearly and work effectively with others to achieve common goals (Dong, 2017). Furthermore, online civic education platforms often provide tools and resources that facilitate real-time collaboration, such as video conferencing, shared documents, and interactive whiteboards, making it easier for students to engage in meaningful dialogue and collective learning experiences. This collaborative approach not only deepens students' understanding of civic concepts but also prepares them to be active and informed participants in their communities, capable of contributing to democratic processes and societal development (Han & Duan, 2017).

The lecturers alluded that online civic education platforms offer a significant benefit by providing diverse learning materials, which enhance the educational experience for both educators and students. One of the lecturers said that:

“These platforms often provide a variety of multimedia resources, including videos, interactive modules, and discussion forums, catering to different learning styles”.

These platforms can curate a wide range of resources, including multimedia content, interactive modules, and up-to-date articles, which cater to different learning styles and preferences. This diversity ensures that learners are exposed to multiple perspectives and sources of information, fostering critical thinking and a more comprehensive understanding of civic issues (Chanda, 2024). Furthermore, the accessibility of these materials allows students from various backgrounds and locations to engage with content that might otherwise be unavailable to them. For educators, the variety of resources simplifies the process of lesson planning and enables the integration of dynamic and engaging materials into their curriculum, ultimately improving teaching effectiveness and student engagement (Sabatier & Jenkins-Smith, 1993). By leveraging the rich and varied content available through online platforms, civic education can become more inclusive, interactive, and impactful, promoting a deeper and more nuanced grasp of civic knowledge and responsibilities.

The study results also revealed that accessibility and flexibility are significant benefits of online civic education platforms, providing numerous advantages to both educators and students. These platforms eliminate geographical barriers, allowing students from diverse and remote locations to access high-quality civic education resources that might otherwise be unavailable. The flexibility of online platforms enables learners to engage with the material at their own pace and on their own schedules, accommodating various learning styles and life commitments, such as work or family responsibilities (Chanda, 2024). This asynchronous nature of online learning fosters a more inclusive educational environment, catering to non-traditional students who may not fit into the conventional classroom setting. Furthermore, online platforms often offer a wide array of multimedia resources, interactive tools, and real-time updates, enriching the learning experience and keeping the content relevant and engaging (Liu & Yuan, 2017). By providing round-the-clock

access to educational materials, online civic education platforms empower students to take control of their learning journey, leading to improved comprehension and retention of civic knowledge and skills.

Figure 1: Benefits of Online Civic Education Platforms

3.1.2 Challenges Faced in Utilizing Online Civic Education Platforms

According to study results, the digital divide represents a significant challenge in utilizing online civic education platforms, particularly in regions with limited access to technology and the internet. This gap, defined by disparities in access to high-speed internet, digital devices, and digital literacy, creates an unequal playing field where some students and educators can fully engage with online civic education resources while others cannot (Şanlı & Mehmet, 2015). In many developing areas, such as rural parts of Zambia, infrastructure deficits and high costs of connectivity hinder the widespread adoption of online learning tools. Consequently, students from these regions often lack the opportunities to develop critical digital skills, participate in interactive online discussions, or access a wealth of educational materials available on the internet. Additionally, even in urban settings, socio-economic factors can limit access, where low-income families may struggle to afford necessary devices and reliable internet services (Chanda & Madoda, 2024). This inequity not only affects student learning outcomes but also poses a challenge to educators who may lack the necessary training and resources to effectively integrate online platforms into their teaching. Addressing the digital divide requires comprehensive strategies,

including investment in infrastructure, affordable internet solutions, and targeted training programs to ensure that all students and educators can benefit from online civic education platforms, thus fostering a more inclusive and equitable educational environment (Smith, 2021)

The findings also noted that technical skills represent a significant challenge in utilizing online civic education platforms. Effective engagement with these platforms often necessitates a foundational understanding of various technologies and digital tools, including web browsers, learning management systems, and multimedia resources. One of the lecturers expressed that:

“Many educators and students may lack the requisite technical proficiency, leading to difficulties in navigating online platforms, accessing and utilizing digital resources, and troubleshooting technical issues. This lack of technical skills can hinder the effective delivery and participation in online civic education, resulting in suboptimal learning experiences and reduced engagement with the content”.

Additionally, disparities in access to technology and internet connectivity further exacerbate these challenges, particularly in underserved or rural areas (Su, 2017). Addressing these issues requires targeted training programs to build digital literacy, alongside efforts to improve technology access and support structures to ensure that all users can effectively engage with online civic education platforms.

Furthermore, engagement is a significant challenge in utilizing online civic education platforms, as it directly impacts the effectiveness and reach of these digital tools in fostering democratic values and civic participation. Swalwell & Payne (2019)' study noted that despite the potential of online platforms to offer flexible and accessible learning opportunities, engaging students in meaningful interaction remains problematic. Several factors contribute to this challenge. To start with, the inherent nature of online learning can lead to feelings of isolation and detachment, which may reduce students' motivation and participation levels compared to traditional face-to-face settings (Zhang, 2024). Additionally, the digital divide, where disparities in access to technology and internet connectivity exist, further exacerbates engagement issues, particularly among students from underprivileged backgrounds. The lack of real-time feedback and the impersonal nature of online communication can also hinder active participation and the development of a sense of community among learners. Moreover, the effectiveness of online platforms depends on their design and the quality of the content delivered, with poorly designed interfaces or inadequate instructional materials potentially leading to disengagement (Sun, 2022). Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach, including improving digital literacy, ensuring equitable access to technology, and designing interactive and compelling content that encourages active participation and fosters a sense of connection among users.

3.1.3 Online Civic Education Platforms and its Impact on Educator Competency

The findings recorded that knowledge enhancement plays a pivotal role in impacting educator competency in utilizing online civic education platforms. When educators engage with these

platforms, they not only access a diverse array of resources and teaching tools but also participate in professional development opportunities that deepen their understanding of education (Zohaib et al, 2024). This enhanced knowledge equips them with a more nuanced grasp of civic concepts, pedagogical strategies, and digital tools, which directly translates into improved instructional practices. By mastering these online platforms, educators can effectively design and deliver engaging civic education content, facilitate interactive discussions, and employ data-driven approaches to assess student understanding. Additionally, the ongoing exposure to emerging trends and best practices in online civic education fosters a culture of continuous learning among educators, thereby elevating their competency and ultimately enriching the learning experience for students (Mtonga & Magasu, 2024). This continuous cycle of knowledge enhancement and application underscores the significant impact that online civic education platforms have on educator effectiveness and student outcomes.

Moving on, pedagogical skills significantly impact educator competency in utilizing online civic education platforms by shaping how effectively educators can engage students and deliver content in a virtual environment. Educators with strong pedagogical skills can tailor their teaching methods to suit online formats, utilizing interactive tools and multimedia resources to enhance learning experiences (Chanda, 2023). Their ability to design and implement engaging online activities, facilitate discussions, and provide timely feedback is crucial in maintaining student motivation and promoting deep understanding of civic concepts. One of the lecturers noted that:

“Effective pedagogical strategies, such as differentiated instruction and formative assessment, enable educators to address diverse learning needs and adapt to varying levels of student participation and comprehension in an online setting”.

Additionally, proficient educators are adept at integrating technology in ways that align with educational goals, fostering a supportive and dynamic online learning community that encourages critical thinking and active citizenship. Thus, the development of pedagogical skills is essential for educators to maximize the potential of online civic education platforms, ensuring that they can deliver content that is both informative and engaging, ultimately enhancing student outcomes in civic education (Mainde & Chola, 2020).

The respondents further observed that professional growth plays a crucial role in enhancing educator competency in utilizing online civic education platforms. As educators engage in continuous professional development, they acquire advanced skills and knowledge that enable them to effectively integrate digital tools into their teaching practices (Magasu et al, 2020). This growth is often facilitated through specialized training programs, workshops, and seminars focused on the latest technologies and pedagogical strategies. By staying updated with evolving digital platforms and educational technologies, educators are better equipped to create engaging and interactive civic education experiences for their students. This professional development not only improves their technical proficiency but also enhances their ability to design and deliver high-quality online content that aligns with educational standards and learning objectives (Zhengyi &

Zhang, 2024). Furthermore, professional growth encourages educators to adopt innovative approaches and critically evaluate the effectiveness of online platforms in achieving desired educational outcomes, ultimately leading to more effective teaching practices and improved student engagement and learning in civic education.

3.2. Impact of Online Civic Education Platforms on Student Learning Outcomes within Selected Higher Learning Institutions

The findings on the impact of online civic education platforms on student learning outcomes can be significant and multifaceted. The findings revealed Engagement and Interaction to be the highest at 32%, Accessibility and Reach at 28%, Skills Development at 20%, Content Delivery and Quality at 15%, and lastly Evaluation and Feedback at 5%. Figure2 below summarized these findings;

Figure2: Impact of Online Civic Education Platforms on Student Learning Outcomes

The findings revealed that engagement and interaction are crucial aspects of online civic education platforms that significantly influence student learning outcomes within higher learning institutions in Zambia. These platforms facilitate an interactive learning environment where students can

engage with course materials, peers, and educators in real time, overcoming geographical and time constraints inherent in traditional learning settings (Schmitt et al, 2024). The dynamic nature of online platforms, including forums, live discussions, and collaborative tools, fosters a participatory learning culture that enhances students' critical thinking and analytical skills. By actively participating in discussions, debates, and interactive activities, students develop a deeper understanding of civic concepts and democratic principles. The use of multimedia resources and interactive simulations further enriches the learning experience, making complex civic topics more accessible and engaging (Chanda et al, 2023). Moreover, the immediate feedback and continuous interaction provided through these platforms allow for personalized learning experiences, addressing individual needs and promoting higher levels of comprehension and retention. This increased engagement and interaction not only contribute to a more comprehensive grasp of civic education content but also empower students to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts, thereby improving their overall learning outcomes (Lu-Ho & Gwo-Jen, 2020).

Additionally, accessibility and reach are critical factors influencing the impact of online civic education platforms on student learning outcomes within selected higher learning institutions in Zambia. These platforms provide a significant opportunity to extend educational resources beyond traditional classroom boundaries, offering students access to a diverse range of civic education materials at any time and from any location with internet connectivity (Torney, 2012). This flexibility is particularly valuable in Zambia, where geographic and infrastructural challenges may otherwise limit students' exposure to quality civic education. One of the students explained that:

“Online platforms enable institutions to overcome physical barriers, reaching students in remote or underserved areas who might not have access to in-person classes or seminars. The ability to engage with multimedia resources, interactive content, and online discussions enhances learning experiences, making civic education more relevant and engaging”.

Moreover, the broad reach of online platforms supports a more inclusive educational environment, accommodating various learning styles and needs, which can contribute to improved understanding and retention of civic concepts. However, the effectiveness of this accessibility depends on the students' digital literacy, the quality of the online content, and the availability of reliable internet access, all of which can influence the overall impact on learning outcomes (Vasiljevic, 2009).

The findings further revealed that online civic education platforms have significantly impacted student learning outcomes in selected higher learning institutions in Zambia, particularly in the realm of skills development. These platforms offer a range of interactive and engaging resources that foster critical thinking, digital literacy, and civic competence. By integrating multimedia elements such as videos, simulations, and discussion forums, these platforms create a dynamic learning environment that enhances students' understanding of civic responsibilities and democratic processes (Katongo et al, 2013). The ability to access diverse perspectives and engage in real-time discussions helps students develop analytical skills and a deeper comprehension of

complex social issues. Furthermore, the flexibility of online learning allows students to work at their own pace, reinforcing their learning and encouraging self-directed study. As a result, students not only acquire theoretical knowledge but also practical skills that are crucial for active participation in civic life. These platforms, therefore, contribute to the holistic development of students, equipping them with the skills necessary for effective citizenship and leadership in their communities (Chanda, 2024).

Moving on, content delivery and quality are pivotal factors in determining the impact of online civic education platforms on student learning outcomes in higher learning institutions in Zambia. These platforms often utilize a range of digital tools and multimedia resources to present educational material, which can enhance engagement and comprehension. Effective content delivery involves structuring information in a coherent, interactive, and accessible manner, ensuring that students can easily navigate through the material and absorb key concepts (Zhu, 2017). The quality of content, including its relevance, accuracy, and depth, directly affects how well students grasp civic education topics and apply them to real-world situations. High-quality online civic education platforms incorporate well-designed curricula, interactive elements like quizzes and discussion forums, and diverse multimedia resources to cater to different learning styles. They also provide timely feedback and support to reinforce learning and address any misunderstandings (Sivis-Cetinkaya, 2019). When content delivery and quality are optimized, students are more likely to develop a strong understanding of civic principles and engage meaningfully with the subject matter, leading to improved learning outcomes and a deeper appreciation of their role as active citizens. In contrast, poorly delivered or low-quality content can hinder learning, resulting in limited student engagement and a shallow grasp of civic concepts (Chanda, 2023). Therefore, the effectiveness of online civic education platforms in enhancing student learning outcomes in Zambia relies heavily on the strategic design and implementation of content delivery and quality.

The results also noted that evaluation and feedback play crucial roles in assessing the impact of online civic education platforms on student learning outcomes within higher learning institutions in Zambia. These platforms facilitate the delivery of civic education through digital means, enabling broader access and flexibility for students (Walsh, 2013). Evaluation involves systematically assessing the effectiveness of these platforms by measuring students' engagement, comprehension, and application of civic concepts. Zheng (2024) says that feedback is integral to this process as it provides students with insights into their performance, helping them understand their strengths and areas for improvement. One of the lecturers alluded that:

“Regular and constructive feedback ensures that students can actively engage with the content, make necessary adjustments, and enhance their learning experience”.

This dynamic interplay of evaluation and feedback helps in identifying best practices, addressing challenges, and continuously refining the online civic education platforms to better meet educational goals (Li, 2021). In the context of Zambian higher learning institutions, such

evaluations and feedback mechanisms are vital for ensuring that these platforms effectively contribute to students' civic knowledge, critical thinking, and active participation in societal matters (Chanda, 2023).

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, assessing the impact of online civic education platforms on educator competency and student outcomes in selected Zambian higher learning institutions reveals significant insights into the transformative potential of digital learning environments. The integration of online platforms has demonstrated a notable enhancement in educator competency by providing access to up-to-date resources, professional development opportunities, and collaborative tools that facilitate innovative teaching methods. Educators have reported improved pedagogical skills and increased engagement in civic education through these digital resources. For students, online civic education platforms have fostered greater accessibility to learning materials, flexibility in studying, and opportunities for interactive and participatory learning experiences. These platforms have contributed to higher levels of civic knowledge, critical thinking, and engagement among students, aligning with educational goals of fostering informed and active citizenship. The study underscores the value of leveraging technology to support both educators and students, highlighting the need for continued investment in digital infrastructure and training to maximize the benefits of online civic education.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study on “the assessment of online civic education platforms and their impact on educator competency and student outcomes in Zambian higher learning institutions”;

1. Enhance Educator Training and Support:

- Institutions should develop comprehensive training programs for educators focused on using online civic education platforms effectively. This should include workshops on digital literacy, instructional design tailored to online platforms, and strategies for engaging students in virtual environments.

2. Strengthen Platform Design and Accessibility:

- Institutions should improve the design and functionality of online civic education platforms to ensure they are user-friendly, accessible, and aligned with educational goals. This includes making platforms compatible with various devices, providing clear navigation, and offering diverse content formats to cater to different learning styles.

3. Evaluate and Monitor Impact Continuously:

- Institutions should implement a robust system for monitoring and evaluating the impact of online civic education platforms on both educator competency and student outcomes. This should include setting clear metrics for success, regularly assessing platform effectiveness, and adjusting strategies based on data-driven insights.

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